

INDUCTION BONDING IN THE PRODUCTION OF ORIENTED POLYPROPYLENE REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Research at the University of Toronto has demonstrated that roll-drawing can markedly improve the uniaxial tensile properties of commodity thermoplastics such as polypropylene (increasing the tensile modulus from 1 to 20 GPa and the tensile strength from 50 to 500 MPa). The possibility of producing laminar composites composed of alternate layers of oriented polypropylene (OPP) sheet and Alclad 2024-T3 aluminum alloy sheet (both 0.3-1 mm thick) was investigated in order to overcome some of OPP's inherent limitations, viz., anisotropic tensile properties and poor compressive properties.

Welds produced using continuous electromagnetic induction bonding had shear strengths around 11 MPa and test failures which occurred cohesively within the OPP material. Conventional adhesive bonding (consisting of phosphoric acid anodizing of aluminum sheet, and dichromate etching of OPP, followed by application of a two part epoxy adhesive) produced joints having shear strengths of 7 MPa and bondline failures at the OPP/adhesive interface.

INTRODUCTION

Production of extended-chain polyethylene fibres by gel spinning is well-known in the field of composites fabrication. In this process polyethylene macromolecules are oriented from a dilute solution so that the chain axis lies along the axis of the fibre; in this way the considerable strength of carbon-carbon bonds can be utilized to nearly their full potential¹. Similarly, by using a roll-drawing process adapted from the metals industry, 0.3 to 2 mm thick uniaxially-oriented polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) sheet have been produced at the University of Toronto. In the case of roll-drawn PP, tensile strength and modulus values up to 0.5 GPa and 20 GPa, respectively²⁻⁵. The two major shortcomings of OPP are (a) poor tensile properties transverse to the drawing direction (strength and modulus: 47 MPa and 2 GPa)^{2,3}, and (b) poor compressive properties⁶.

The combination of oriented polypropylene (OPP) with aluminum (Al) in the form of alternating (0.3-0.5 mm thick) lamina could provide designers with a material which has the processability of sheet Al (machinability, formability) but with tensile strength, fracture toughness, and fatigue properties exceeding those of monolithic Al. Indeed, the recently introduced ARALL (Aramid Reinforced Aluminum Laminate) has done just this⁷. Aramid fibres are expensive and this limits ARALL's applicability to aerospace structures. This paper examines the development of OPP/Al laminates capable of supplying mass market structural applications. The first step is to be able to bond OPP to Al; this is not as easy a task as one might expect.

THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

1. Bonding of Polypropylene

PP is difficult to bond because (a) its low surface energy (31 mJ/m²) leads to poor wettability of the surface by conventional adhesives, and (b) the lack of polar groups or active sites on the polymer chains prevents the formation of chemical bonds⁹. Upon orientation, these problems increase and it has been demonstrated by Lew¹⁰ that the surface energy is further decreased to 21 mJ/m². An added problem is that the oriented,

fibrillar arrangement of OPP is disrupted by excessive heating and reverts to the thermodynamically-preferred spherulitic structure, thus losing its enhanced mechanical properties.

2. Conventional Solutions to Polypropylene Bonding

Surface treatments such as cold gas plasma, corona discharge, dichromate etching, and flame can be used to increase the wettability of the polyolefin surface and introduce active sites to it for chemical bonding to an adhesive⁷. Alternatively, a more bondable grade of polypropylene resin can be chosen prior to roll-drawing, i.e., copolymers of PP with acrylic acid, maleic anhydride¹¹, or methyl-1,4-hexadiene¹² provide active groups which can enhance the bondability of these materials with conventional thermoset adhesives.

3. An Alternative Approach

The authors have devised an alternative bonding technique which involves the following:
A) thorough cleaning and phosphoric acid anodizing of the Al sheet to produce a micro-rough, porous oxide coating¹³;

B) the use of high frequency, transverse flux induction heating¹⁴ to generate localized heat at the OPP/Al interface; and

C) the application of pressure to the adherends as they pass over the heating area (this insures that the surfaces to be bonded remain in intimate contact during heating). The bond is formed when a thin layer of OPP is melted at the Al interface. The molten PP layer flows into the porous oxide layer on the metal surface and solidifies forming a mechanical bond while chain entanglements join it to the OPP material.

EQUIPMENT DESIGN

The inductor used was a rectangular (107 mm X 80 mm), flat, four turn, pancake coil machined from 10 mm thick copper plate. This was mounted flush in a PE block and covered with 0.8 mm thick PTFE to isolate the induction coil from the workpiece. PTFE was also used to isolate the turns of the coil from each other. Two sets of rubber-coated rollers driven by a continuously variable DC motor through a pulley system comprised the drive system. Pressure was applied by an "Enerpac" hydraulic jack whose load was transferred to two PE rollers located directly above the PE block containing the coil. A schematic drawing of the apparatus is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of continuous electromagnetic induction bonding apparatus .

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

1. Aluminum Preparation

Alclad 2024-T3 sheet 0.4 mm thick was used throughout. Sheets measuring 127 mm X 406 mm were cut and degreased by solvent wiping using 1,1,1-trichloroethane. The sheets were then etched in an aqueous solution of 250 g/L of sodium hydroxide at room temperature for ten minutes^{15,16} instead of the usually used FPL etch¹⁷. The sheets were then desmutted by dipping them in an aqueous solution of 50% nitric acid by volume and rinsing them in tap water. Three sheets at a time were then anodized in a 316L stainless steel tank containing an aqueous solution of 10% by weight of 85% phosphoric acid, for 25 minutes at

15±1V on Al racks. Subsequently, the sheets were dipped in an aqueous solution containing 15 ppm of nitrilotris methylene phosphonic acid (minimizing the effects of ageing of the coatings due to hydration¹⁸). Finally, the sheets were dried in an oven at 90 °C for two hours and stored in a dessicator prior to bonding.

2. Oriented Polypropylene Preparation

OPP sheets measuring 130 mm x 590 mm with draw ratios in the range 10 to 12 were solvent wiped using acetone. Two pieces of OPP were used, one on either side of the Al sheet, so that the hot Al surface would not damage the rubber-coated traction rollers or the PE pressure rollers.

3. Welding

The induction unit used was a 450 kHz TOCCO model #2EG051. The effect of heat input variation was examined in the first test series. The power output of the induction unit was maximized by inductively matching the work coil to the rest of the tank circuit and the power output was kept constant throughout all further experiments. The travel speed was varied from 1.5 to 2.5 mm/s and the roll pressure was held constant at 120 kPa. The effect of roll pressure was examined in the second test series. The roll pressure was varied from 0 to 300 kPa at a constant travel speed of 2 mm/s.

4. Lap Shear Sample Preparation

Samples were prepared from three-ply laminates according to ASTM D3165-73. The notches were cut carefully through two lamina on one side and through one on the other so that only the bottom interface was tested consistently (see Fig.2). The samples were tested in tension using an Instron testing machine at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min.

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of 3-ply lap shear sample configuration

5. Cohesive Shear Testing

The cohesive shear strength of roll-drawn OPP as a function of draw ratio was evaluated in order to examine the effectiveness of induction bonding operations. Test specimens measuring 25.4 X 18.0 mm having thicknesses from 0.87-1.83 mm were machined with the notches 12.7 mm apart so that the notch tips both intercepted a common plane through the centre of the material (see ASTM D3846-79). The samples were tested in tension at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min. A steel jig of the type described in ASTM D695M-85 was used to prevent the peeling action which is always associated with lap shear testing. In these tests the draw ratio was varied from 4 to 20.

6. Transmitted Light Microscopy

Coupons measuring 15 X 25.4 mm were cut from failed lap shear specimens in areas immediately adjacent to the lap region. These coupons were immersed in an aqueous solution containing 500 g/L of sodium hydroxide at 60-80 °C to dissolve the Al sheet. The OPP bondline region was examined by microtoming 25 µm thick sections parallel to the direction of orientation. These were then viewed under cross-polarized light.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results from the lap shear tests done on the two series of bonds are shown in Fig. 3 (a) and Fig. 3 (b). Fig. 3 (a) shows that at low travel speeds (or high heat inputs) the bonds had moderate shear strength values. The optimum bond strength of 10.3 MPa was achieved at a travel speed of 2 mm/s. At speeds greater than 2.4 mm/s the bond strength eventually falls to zero since insufficient inductive heating occurs at the Al surface to melt the OPP. Conversely, at a travel speed of 1.5 mm/s excessive disorientation, melting, and interface bubble formation was observed. All bonds in this test series failed cohesively in the OPP.

The role of applied pressure in the formation of OPP/Al bonds is primarily to bring the mating surfaces into intimate contact. OPP/Al bonding did not occur if no pressure (0 kPa) was applied during the welding operation. As little as 60 kPa was sufficient to bring the mating surfaces together to form a bond. It should

be noted, however, that at this pressure some of the failures observed were of a mixed cohesive and adhesive (interfacial) nature. One adhesive/cohesive failure was also observed at 180 kPa; all other failures in this test series occurred cohesively within the OPP.

Fig. 4 shows the variation of OPP cohesive shear strength as a function of draw ratio. Although we know that OPP tensile strength and modulus values increase dramatically with increasing draw ratio the shear strength increases only slightly. At a draw ratio of 12 the shear strength is 10.2 MPa which correlates well with the shear strengths achieved with bonds made at a travel speed of 2 and 2.4 mm/s. For disoriented material (ie. draw ratio=1). The extrapolated shear strength of unoriented polypropylene is 8.6 MPa and this lies within the 95% confidence limits of the bonds made at 1.5 mm/s (7.7 ± 1.0 MPa). This suggests that at low travel speeds the OPP becomes unoriented and begins to recrystallize throughout its thickness. The low shear strength bonds produced at this travel speed are largely attributable to this loss of orientation. However, the formation of bubbles in the material also contributed to poor shear strength values. This loss of orientation was observed, to varying degrees in all sections viewed under cross-polarized light.

A typical microtomed cross-section is shown in Fig. 5. Three regions were observed, viz., (a) the fusion zone, (b) the heat affected zone (HAZ), and (c) the bulk OPP. In the fusion zone the PP was completely melted and recrystallized. Three distinct sub-regions can be seen within this zone: (a) a transcrystalline region adjacent to the Al surface, (b) a region in which spherulites had grown randomly in the plane of the cross-section, and (c) another transcrystalline region adjacent to the partially oriented PP of the HAZ. These transcrystalline regions have been observed during compression moulding when polyolefins are cast against metal surfaces¹⁹. Many crystallites are nucleated at the Al surface and grow in an oriented fashion into the melt. It is interesting to note that a similar structure was formed adjacent to the fibrillar OPP; this indicates that a similar nucleation effect is also occurring at this interface.

No clear correlation was observed between the size of fusion zones or HAZ regions and travel speed or roll pressure. The design of the induction coil was insufficiently optimized to produce an even temperature profile across the width of the bonded area on the sheets and this probably explains this lack of correlation in test results. The thickness of the fusion zone ranged from 32 to 300 μm and the HAZ thickness was as low as 16 μm .

Fig. 3 (a) Plot showing the effect of travel speed on lap shear strength of the bonds
(b) Plot showing the effect of roll pressure on the lap shear strength of the bonds

Fig. 4 Plot showing the variation of the cohesive shear strength of OPP with draw ratio

Fig. 5 Transmitted light photomicrograph showing a typical cross-section through bonded OPP with (a) formerly Al; (b) fusion zone with (i) transcrystalline region nucleated by Al surface, (ii) randomly oriented spherulites in plane of cross-section, and (iii) second transcrystalline region apparently nucleated by OPP; (c) partially disoriented HAZ; and (d) fully oriented bulk OPP.

CONCLUSIONS

The shear strength of induction bonded OPP/Al joints produced at optimum conditions (2 mm/s travel speed, 120kPa roll pressure) compare favourably with the strengths measured for similar laminates produced by a conventional adhesive bonding technique (dichromate etching of OPP, anodization of Al, with a rubber-toughened, room temperature cured epoxy adhesive)²⁰ The shear strengths achieved by the two bonding methods were 10.3 ± 1.6 MPa and 7.0 ± 1.9 MPa, respectively. The shear strengths of the induction bonded joints correlated well to the directly measured values of the cohesive shear strength of the monolithic OPP. Transmitted light microscopy of cross-sections through the OPP revealed three distinct regions: (a) a fusion zone, (b) a heat affected zone, and (c) the bulk OPP. Closer examination of the fusion zone revealed

three sub-regions: (a) a transcrystalline region nucleated at the Al interface, (b) a spherulitic region, and (c) a second transcrystalline region adjacent to the heat-affected zone region of the OPP.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to sincerely thank ALCAN INTERNATIONAL, the National Science & Engineering Research Council, the Welding Research Council of the American Welding Society, and the government of the province of Ontario (through its URIF programme) for having financially supported this work.

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